

EBFMC25-OP-30 · Goiter and Pulmonary Nodule in a Patient Presenting with Persistent Throat Irritation: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Persistent throat irritation and dry cough are common symptoms encountered in daily clinical practice, with a wide range of etiological factors.

Case Presentation: This case report describes a patient who initially sought symptomatic treatment but was subsequently diagnosed with hypothyroidism, an angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor-induced cough, and a pulmonary nodule through a comprehensive clinical evaluation.

Discussion: A multidisciplinary approach facilitated the identification of underlying systemic conditions and optimized the management process through appropriate referrals.

Conclusion: This case underscores the importance of thorough patient assessment in family medicine practice and highlights the necessity of considering a broad differential diagnosis in patients presenting with seemingly benign symptoms.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Goiter, ACE inhibitor, pulmonary nodule, family medicine, multidisciplinary approach

INTRODUCTION

This case report aims to underscore the significance of differential diagnosis in patients presenting with similar symptoms and to highlight the necessity of a multidisciplinary approach in family medicine practice.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 57-year-old male patient presented to our outpatient clinic with complaints of persistent throat irritation and dry cough lasting for the past two months. Initially, the patient sought only symptomatic relief with a throat spray containing flurbiprofen; however, a comprehensive history and physical examination indicated the necessity for further evaluation.

The patient's symptoms had been ongoing for approximately two months, with throat irritation and dry cough being the predominant complaints. The cough, which was particularly aggravated at night and triggered by speaking, caused sleep disturbances. He had been on perindopril therapy for hypertension for the past two months and noticed that his cough commenced following the initiation of the medication, though he had not associated it directly with the drug. He had not previously sought medical attention for similar complaints. Additionally, he reported occasional episodes of shortness of breath but denied symptoms such as sputum production, chest pain, or wheezing. The patient had a history of smoking amounting to 20 pack-years and was an active smoker. There was no family history of malignancy or thyroid disease.

Upon physical examination, the patient appeared in good general condition, alert, cooperative, and oriented. His vital signs were as follows: blood pressure 132/84 mmHg, pulse rate 78 bpm, respiratory rate 18 breaths per minute, body temperature 36.7°C, and oxygen saturation 97%. Neck examination revealed diffuse thyroid enlargement with a mildly firm and non-tender consistency. No cervical lymphadenopathy was detected, and oropharyngeal examination was unremarkable. Pulmonary examination revealed normal bilateral breath sounds without adventitious sounds. Systemic examination findings were otherwise unremarkable.

Laboratory investigations demonstrated a TSH level of 9.94 μ IU/mL and a T4 level of 0.9 ng/dL. A chest radiograph performed due to his complaints of shortness of breath revealed a 0.5 \times 0.5 cm pulmonary nodule in the right apical region. The patient was diagnosed with hypothyroidism, and levothyroxine sodium therapy was initiated. He was referred to the endocrinology department for thyroid ultrasonography. Given the suspected etiology, the ACE inhibitor (perindopril) was discontinued and replaced with an angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB). Additionally, the patient was referred to the pulmonology department for further evaluation and management of the pulmonary nodule.

RESULTS

Comprehensive clinical evaluation of the patient revealed that the presenting symptoms were multifactorial in origin. Laboratory analyses indicated a thyrotropin (TSH) level of 9.94 μ IU/mL, exceeding the reference range, and a free thyroxine (fT4) level of 0.9 ng/dL, which was below the normal range, supporting a diagnosis of primary hypothyroidism. A chest radiograph, performed due to the patient's respiratory complaints, demonstrated a 0.5 \times 0.5 cm pulmonary nodule in the right apical region, lacking irregular borders.

Detailed medication history revealed that the patient had been using perindopril for the past two months, with the onset of dry cough coinciding with the initiation of this medication. Given the clinical presentation and temporal association, ACE inhibitor-induced cough was suspected, leading to discontinuation of the drug and replacement with an angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB). Follow-up evaluations revealed marked improvement in cough symptoms after the medication adjustment.

The patient was managed based on the following preliminary diagnoses:

- Primary hypothyroidism: Levothyroxine therapy was initiated, and the patient was referred to the endocrinology outpatient clinic for further evaluation and follow-up.
- Chronic dry cough secondary to ACE inhibitor: Given the suspected drug-induced etiology, pharmacological management was revised accordingly.
- Incidental pulmonary nodule: Considering the patient's status as a current smoker with a 20 pack-year history, he was categorized as being at increased risk for malignancy. Consequently, he was referred to the pulmonology outpatient clinic for low-dose thoracic computed tomography and further monitoring.

This clinical presentation demonstrates that superficial evaluation of symptoms may obscure serious underlying systemic pathologies. A holistic and multidisciplinary approach significantly enhances diagnostic accuracy and patient management in family medicine practice.

DISCUSSION

Throat irritation and dry cough are nonspecific symptoms that may arise from a wide range of etiologies. In this case, these symptoms were found to be associated with multiple underlying pathologies, necessitating a comprehensive approach to diagnosis and management:

- ACE Inhibitor-Induced Cough: This condition is attributed to the accumulation of bradykinin and substance P, which can lead to persistent cough (Alp, Karahan, & Kalçık, 2018).
- Hypothyroidism and Its Respiratory Implications: Hypothyroidism can contribute to mucosaledema, dyspnea, and impaired pulmonary function. (Yılmaz, Adas, Helvacı, Altıntaş, & Günaldi, 2013)
- Diffuse Thyroid Enlargement: Enlargement of the thyroid gland may exert compressive effect on adjacent anatomical structures, resulting in dysphagia, dyspnea, and voice alterations. (Menekşe, 2018)
- Pulmonary Nodule: The presence of a pulmonary nodule in a patient with a significant smoking history warrants careful monitoring due to the potential risk of malignancy. While small nodules are generally considered low risk, those detected in smokers require close surveillance (Verim, Kara, & Sarı, 2012).

The Fleischner Society Guidelines serve as a valuable reference for the management of pulmonary nodules. According to the latest recommendations:

- Nodules <6 mm are generally considered low risk and do not typically necessitate follow-up.
- In high-risk individuals, such as smokers, low-dose thoracic CT at 3- to 6-month intervals is recommended.
- Nodules measuring 6-8 mm should be reassessed with follow-up CT every 6-12 months to monitor for changes in size or morphology.
- Nodules >8 mm require more detailed evaluation due to an increased risk of malignancy. Advanced imaging techniques such as PET-CT, as well as biopsy, should be considered based on the radiological characteristics of the nodule. (MacMahon et al., 2017)

CONCLUSION

This case underscores the critical role of family medicine beyond symptomatic management, emphasizing its contribution to comprehensive patient evaluation through a multidisciplinary approach. As the first point of contact between patients and the healthcare system, family physicians play an essential role in early diagnosis and intervention, highlighting the importance of a detailed clinical history and thorough physical examination. (Çaylan, 2016)

Given the long-term pulmonary effects of smoking, routine surveillance is crucial for patients with detected pulmonary nodules. Additionally, patient education regarding potential medication side effects, coupled with a multidisciplinary treatment approach, significantly enhances early disease recognition and management. Maintaining high clinical suspicion, ensuring appropriate utilization of advanced imaging, and implementing systematic follow-up strategies are imperative in preventing complications and optimizing patient outcomes.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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